

The Planning and Coordinating Roles of Instructional Leadership in Managing Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study examined the planning and coordinating roles of instructional leadership in managing non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. School management involves the systematic coordination of human, material, and financial resources to achieve educational goals effectively. It encompasses planning, organizing, staffing, supervising, and evaluating processes that collectively enhance school productivity and service delivery. Effective management fosters discipline, teamwork, and motivation among staff and students, thereby creating an enabling environment for academic excellence. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to collect data from principals' opinions and experiences regarding how non-professional teachers are managed for effective service delivery. The population of the study comprised all 350 principals of senior secondary schools in Rivers State (241 males and 109 females), as obtained from the Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board (2024). A census sampling technique was adopted because of the small population size. Data were collected using a 10-item self-constructed questionnaire titled Managing Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery Questionnaire (MNTESDQ), structured on a 4-point modified Likert scale. The instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Educational Management, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, and its reliability, determined using the test-retest method and Cronbach Alpha was employed, which yielded a coefficient of .951, indicating high reliability. Out of 350 questionnaires administered, 345 were returned, representing a 98.57% response rate. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while independent sample t-tests tested the hypotheses at a .05 significance level. Findings emphasized that effective school management significantly enhances instructional delivery, promotes teacher efficiency, and improves educational outcomes in public schools. The findings revealed that planning and coordinating roles of instructional leadership in managing non-professional teachers enhance effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study recommended that principals of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State should strengthen strategic planning practices and implement systematic coordination.

Keywords: Planning, Coordinating Roles, School Management, Instructional Leadership, Service Delivery, Non-Professional Teachers, Rivers State.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is universally recognized as the foundation for national growth and sustainable development. It serves as a vital instrument for social, economic, and political transformation. The effectiveness of any nation's educational system depends largely on the quality of its teachers, the efficiency of its leadership, and the soundness of its institutional management practices. In Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, concerns have been raised about the effectiveness of service delivery in public senior secondary schools due to the increasing employment of non-professional teachers, who are those without requisite pedagogical training or certification in education. Such teachers often lack the methodological competence, classroom management skills, and assessment literacy necessary for quality teaching and learning. Consequently, the role of instructional leadership becomes indispensable in ensuring that non-professional teachers perform effectively to achieve institutional goals (Adebayo & Oyeniran, 2022).

Instructional leadership is a critical dimension of educational management that focuses primarily on teaching and learning processes within schools. It involves the principal's ability to plan, coordinate, supervise, and evaluate instructional activities to enhance student achievement and teacher effectiveness (Hallinger & Murphy, 2013). According to Leithwood et al. (2020), instructional leadership is one of the most influential factors in improving teacher performance and student outcomes because it focuses on the core business of schools (teaching and learning). When managing non-professional teachers, instructional leadership provides the structure, guidance, and motivation needed to promote effective classroom practices and professional conduct.

The planning and coordinating roles of instructional leadership are fundamental to ensuring effective educational management. Planning involves setting clear objectives, designing instructional timetables, allocating resources, and providing a roadmap for achieving desired learning outcomes. It enables school leaders to anticipate challenges, align teaching objectives with curriculum standards, and establish professional development strategies (Bush, 2011). In managing non-professional teachers, instructional planning ensures that teaching goals are well-structured and that teachers are adequately supported through mentorship, supervision, and in-service training (Okon, 2019). Through strategic planning, principals can design instructional schedules, monitor curriculum delivery, and develop capacity-building initiatives that help non-professional teachers acquire essential pedagogical skills.

Coordination, on the other hand, involves harmonizing various instructional activities, promoting collaboration among teachers, and ensuring consistency in teaching practices across subjects and grade levels. It enables principals to integrate teaching and assessment processes, ensuring that instructional objectives are aligned with student learning needs and curriculum standards. Coordination also ensures that teachers both professional and non-professional work collectively toward achieving common goals (Robinson et al., 2008). Through the effective coordination of instructional programmes, school leaders can foster a collegial atmosphere where non-professional teachers receive ongoing feedback, participate in collaborative lesson planning, and develop assessment literacy through shared professional experiences (Adeyemi, 2020).

However, in many public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, challenges persist in the management of non-professional teachers. Many principals face difficulties related to inadequate teacher preparation, lack of motivation, and limited understanding of modern instructional strategies. These challenges often result in poor curriculum delivery and low student performance (Nwogbo & Ogbonna, 2021). Non-professional teachers may also struggle with classroom discipline, lesson planning, and learner assessment, which negatively impacts the overall quality of education. To address these issues, effective instructional leadership practices anchored on proper

planning and coordination are required to strengthen instructional supervision, mentoring, and evaluation (Hallinger, 2018).

Effective service delivery in education refers to the degree to which schools achieve their instructional and developmental goals through efficient teaching, adequate supervision, and measurable learning outcomes (Olatunji, 2021). It involves not only delivering content knowledge but also fostering student engagement, teacher commitment, and institutional efficiency. When instructional leadership functions are properly exercised through strategic planning and coordinated management, schools are better positioned to improve teacher effectiveness and ensure high standards of educational delivery (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

Statement of the Problem

Effective instructional leadership is fundamental to the realization of educational goals in secondary schools. However, in Rivers State, many public senior secondary schools are confronted with challenges stemming from the increasing employment of non-professional teachers, who are individuals who lack formal pedagogical training and certification. These teachers often struggle with instructional planning, classroom management, and assessment literacy, leading to inconsistencies in curriculum delivery and declining educational outcomes. Despite the vital role of instructional leadership in guiding and supporting teachers, evidence suggests that many principals do not adequately apply effective planning and coordinating strategies to manage non-professional teachers.

The poor instructional planning in secondary schools have resulted in unclear teaching objectives, inadequate lesson organization, and insufficient supervision of non-professional teachers. Similarly, weak coordination limits collaboration among teachers, leading to fragmented instructional practices and ineffective classroom delivery. Consequently, students' academic performance and overall service delivery in many public schools remain below expectation. While studies have emphasized the importance of instructional leadership in improving teacher effectiveness, limited research has specifically examined how principals' planning and coordinating roles influence the management of non-professional teachers in Rivers State. This gap in knowledge underscores the need to investigate the extent to which instructional leadership practices are utilized to enhance effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools.

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study was to examine the planning and coordinating roles of instructional leadership in managing non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically the objectives are to:

- Establish the extent planning instructional leadership is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Determine the extent coordinating assessment literacy is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- To what extent is planning instructional leadership used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent is coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study at 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning instructional leadership is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent coordinating assessment literacy is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Instructional Leadership Model (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985)

Instructional Leadership Model was developed by Hallinger and Murphy in 1985 and their work have remained one of the most influential frameworks for understanding how school leaders promote effective teaching and learning. It positions the principal as the central figure in directing, coordinating, and enhancing instructional processes within the school. The model emphasizes that the effectiveness of a school largely depends on the instructional leadership capacity of its principal, particularly their ability to plan, coordinate, supervise, and evaluate teaching and learning activities. Unlike administrative or managerial leadership that focuses on maintaining structures, instructional leadership is primarily concerned with improving classroom instruction and student outcomes.

Hallinger and Murphy (1985) model was conceptualized around three core dimensions: (1) defining the school's mission, (2) managing the instructional programme, and (3) promoting a positive school learning climate. Each of these dimensions captures essential leadership behaviors that directly influence teacher performance, instructional quality, and student achievement.

The first dimension of the model defines a school's mission, which involves establishing clear and measurable educational goals and communicating them effectively to teachers and other stakeholders. According to Hallinger (2011), effective instructional leaders develop a shared vision that aligns teachers' efforts toward improving learning outcomes. This process includes setting academic expectations, clarifying roles, and ensuring that both professional and non-professional teachers understand the school's instructional priorities. In contexts like Rivers State, where some teachers lack formal pedagogical training, defining a clear mission provides direction and purpose. It enables non-professional teachers to understand their instructional responsibilities and align their classroom activities with institutional goals.

The second dimension of the model explains the management of instructional programme, which is represented the heart of instructional leadership. It includes supervising instruction, coordinating curriculum implementation, and monitoring student progress. Principals are expected to provide ongoing instructional support by observing classroom practices, giving feedback, and ensuring that teachers adhere to curriculum standards (Bush, 2011). For non-professional teachers,

effective instructional management provides the necessary structure and guidance for lesson delivery. Principals play a vital role in planning instructional timetables, organizing professional development programmes, and ensuring effective resource utilization. According to Okon (2019), instructional management is essential for bridging competence gaps among non-professional teachers through supervision, mentoring, and regular in-service training.

The third dimension of the model illuminates the promotion positive school learning climate that focuses on creating an environment conducive to teaching and learning. This involves fostering teacher collaboration, recognizing instructional achievements, and maintaining high expectations for student performance. Hallinger and Murphy (2013) argued that a positive learning climate enhances teacher motivation and encourages innovation in instructional practices. When school leaders promote collegiality and teamwork, non-professional teachers are more likely to develop confidence and improve their classroom delivery. Furthermore, maintaining discipline, providing instructional materials, and ensuring fair evaluation practices contribute to a supportive climate where both teachers and students can thrive.

The key strength of the Instructional Leadership Model lies in its emphasis on systematic planning and coordination of teaching and learning. Effective principals use structured planning to align curriculum goals with instructional activities to allocate teaching responsibilities and design assessment strategies. Coordination in this context ensures that teaching, learning, and evaluation processes function harmoniously towards the achievement of educational objectives. Leithwood et al. (2020) noted that instructional leadership integrates planning and coordination to promote coherence and accountability across the school systems. These functions are crucial for maintaining instructional quality and consistency in schools with non-professional teachers.

The model also highlights the prominence and processes of data-driven decision-making. As such, instructional leaders are able to identify weaknesses in teaching and implement targeted interventions by monitoring student performance and analyzing assessment results (Robinson et al., 2008). This is particularly relevant in the management of non-professional teachers, because it allows principals to provide evidence-based feedback that enhances instructional competence. Thus, coordinating assessment literacy in schools is an extension of instructional leadership that ensures that teachers understand how to interpret assessment data and use it to inform teaching practices (Adeyemi, 2020).

Also, Instructional Leadership Model is said to align with contemporary educational accountability demands. It emphasizes the principal's role as a change agent that influences teaching practices through vision, collaboration, and instructional supervision (Ololube, 2011). Hallinger (2018) observed that instructional leadership bridges the gap between administrative management and pedagogical improvement, ensuring that leadership practices translate directly into enhanced classroom learning. In the Nigerian educational context, where schools face challenges of inadequate teacher preparation, poor motivation, and limited resources, the instructional leadership model provides a practical framework for improving service delivery.

However, the successful implementation of instructional leadership depends on contextual factors such as principal training, school culture, and resource availability. In many public senior secondary schools, principals juggle administrative, financial, and instructional responsibilities, often limiting the time devoted to direct instructional leadership. Despite these challenges, Hallinger and Murphy model remains relevant because it provides a structured approach that emphasizes teaching and learning as the core mission of schools.

Therefore, Instructional Leadership Model offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing how principals influence teaching quality and student outcomes through planning, coordination, supervision, and effective and conducive school climate. The model's importance are of necessity

for instructional focus, the collaboration, and the professional development processes as they patterned to the essential strategies for managing both professional and non-professional teachers (Ololube, 2011). In addition, the model provides valuable insights into how principals can and are able to strengthen instructional leadership practices that enhance effective service delivery and promote sustainable educational excellence.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Management of School

School management in the context of this research refers to the systematic process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling the human, material, and financial resources within a school to achieve its educational goals effectively and efficiently. According to Okeke (2020), it is a dynamic process that involves the coordination of various administrative and instructional activities to ensure the smooth functioning of the school system. Effective school management creates environment that are conducive for teaching and learning, where both teachers and students can perform optimally (Ololube, 2017).

According to Nwankwo (2019), the management of a school encompasses several key functions, including planning, which involves setting educational goals and developing strategies to achieve them; organizing, which ensures the allocation of responsibilities and resources; staffing, which entails the recruitment and development of competent personnel; supervision, which ensures adherence to educational standards; and evaluation, which assesses performance and outcomes. These functions collectively ensure that the school operates efficiently and achieves its academic and developmental objectives.

A well-managed school also fosters effective communication, teamwork, and participatory decision-making among stakeholders such as principals, teachers, students, parents, and the community. As noted by Bush (2011), successful school management is characterized by strong leadership, accountability, transparency, and continuous improvement. Moreover, it integrates both administrative and instructional leadership to enhance the quality of education.

Especially in secondary schools, effective school management is essential for addressing challenges such as inadequate funding, teacher shortage, and poor infrastructure. Principals who apply sound management principles in balancing human relations with administrative control promote teacher motivation, student discipline, and overall institutional effectiveness (Ogunyinka, 2021). As a result, school management is not merely an administrative function, rather, it is a strategic process aimed at achieving educational excellence and societal development.

Planning Instructional Leadership and the Management of Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

Instructional planning is a crucial function of school leadership that provides the foundation for effective teaching and learning. It involves setting educational goals, developing strategies, allocating resources, and creating structures that guide teachers toward achieving institutional objectives. In public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, where the teaching workforce increasingly includes non-professional teachers, the extent to which principals employ planning as an aspect of instructional leadership significantly determines the effectiveness of service delivery. Non-professional teachers often lack formal pedagogical training, requiring school leaders to adopt deliberate planning approaches to integrate them effectively into the instructional process (Adebayo

& Oyeniran, 2022).

Planning as a leadership function entails identifying instructional needs, setting priorities, and aligning school programmes with national education standards. Bush (2011) emphasizes that planning provides a systematic approach for achieving educational outcomes by ensuring that instructional activities are organized and coherent. In schools with non-professional teachers, effective planning helps define teaching roles, clarify expectations, and allocate teaching responsibilities based on individual competencies. Through structured lesson schedules, professional development plans, and instructional supervision timetables, principals can enhance the instructional performance of non-professional teachers and ensure consistency in curriculum delivery (Okon, 2019).

The effectiveness of instructional planning also depends on the principal's ability to anticipate challenges and develop proactive strategies. Non-professional teachers, due to limited training, may find it difficult to design lesson plans or apply learner-centered methodologies. Hence, principals must plan continuous in-service training, peer mentoring, and classroom observation programmes that build the capacity of these teachers. Adeyemi (2020) notes that instructional planning provides a framework for identifying skill gaps and implementing remedial interventions, thereby improving teacher performance and student learning outcomes. Principals are able to ensure that non-professional teachers are not excluded from quality improvement initiatives by integrating professional development into school plans.

Moreover, instructional planning serves as a mechanism for goal alignment and accountability. Through effective planning, school leaders communicate clear instructional objectives and establish performance indicators for both professional and non-professional teachers. According to Hallinger and Murphy (2013), goal-oriented planning enhances teachers' sense of purpose and direction, fostering commitment to institutional goals. For non-professional teachers, structured planning ensures clarity in lesson delivery and assessment procedures, reducing ambiguity and promoting effective service delivery. When plans are properly documented and monitored, they serve as guiding tools for instructional consistency across subjects and classes.

In Rivers State, however, the extent to which principals employ systematic instructional planning remains inconsistent. Some schools have well-structured instructional plans with clear supervision frameworks, while others operate with minimal documentation and informal planning processes. This inconsistency often affects the management of non-professional teachers, leading to irregular teaching schedules, poor instructional monitoring, and low accountability (Nwogbo & Ogbonna, 2021). A lack of strategic planning also results in ineffective deployment of human and material resources, which ultimately impairs school performance.

Furthermore, instructional planning enhances collaboration among teachers. When properly implemented, planning sessions provide opportunities for joint lesson preparation, exchange of ideas, and collective problem-solving. Robinson, Lloyd, and Rowe (2008) assert that collaborative planning improves teacher confidence and promotes the sharing of best practices. For non-professional teachers, participating in collaborative planning allows them to learn from experienced colleagues, thereby improving their instructional competence. Principals who plan collaboratively foster a culture of teamwork and continuous improvement, which is essential for effective service delivery.

Ultimately, the extent of instructional planning reflects the leadership capacity of school heads. Principals who engage in comprehensive planning are better positioned to manage diverse teacher categories, address instructional challenges, and sustain quality standards. As Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins (2020) observe, effective planning is a hallmark of successful instructional leadership because it integrates goal setting, capacity building, and monitoring into the daily

operations of the school. In the context of Rivers State, planning instructional leadership therefore serves as the foundation upon which non-professional teachers can be guided, supported, and supervised toward achieving effective educational service delivery.

Coordinating Assessment Literacy in the Management of Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

Assessment literacy is the ability of teachers to design, administer, interpret, and use assessment data to improve teaching and learning. Coordination of assessment literacy by instructional leaders ensures that assessment practices are standardized, meaningful, and aligned with curriculum goals. In public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, where many non-professional teachers are engaged in instructional delivery, coordination of assessment literacy becomes a vital leadership function for ensuring quality education. Since non-professional teachers often lack sufficient training in assessment methods, effective coordination by school principals is crucial for promoting consistent and valid evaluation practices (Hallinger, 2018).

Coordination in instructional leadership involves harmonizing diverse instructional and evaluative activities to achieve institutional goals. It ensures that all teachers, regardless of qualification, adhere to uniform standards of lesson delivery, assessment, and record keeping (Bush, 2011). When principals coordinate assessment literacy, they organize workshops, develop assessment templates, and ensure that grading systems align with state and national standards. According to Robinson et al. (2008), strong coordination enhances the coherence of teaching practices and ensures that student assessments reflect actual learning outcomes. For non-professional teachers, coordination provides the structure and support necessary to implement assessment effectively.

Assessment literacy coordination also involves the integration of formative and summative evaluation processes. Leithwood and Jantzi (2006) posited that principals play a critical role in guiding teachers to use assessment results for instructional improvement. Through coordinated assessment systems, principals help non-professional teachers understand how to use test data to identify students' learning needs, adjust teaching strategies, and improve lesson effectiveness. Regular coordination meetings, peer assessments, and moderation sessions enable non-professional teachers to improve their judgment of student performance and align their assessments with curriculum objectives (Adeyemi, 2020).

Furthermore, coordination fosters consistency and accountability in school-based assessments. Many non-professional teachers may rely on subjective or inconsistent grading methods due to limited understanding of evaluation principles. Principals who coordinate assessment literacy provide standardized rubrics, mark schemes, and performance benchmarks that ensure fairness and reliability in assessment. Okon (2019) noted that such coordination also enhances teachers' confidence in using assessment data for feedback and reporting. It helps establish a culture of evidence-based instruction, where decisions about teaching strategies and student interventions are guided by assessment results.

In the Rivers State educational context, however, the extent of coordinated assessment literacy among school leaders varies widely. Some principals actively organize professional development workshops on assessment, while others focus primarily on administrative duties. This variation affects how non-professional teachers implement assessment practices in their classrooms. Inadequate coordination often leads to disparities in grading, poor feedback systems, and lack of data-driven instructional improvement (Nwogbo & Ogbonna, 2021). Such deficiencies reduce the reliability of student evaluation and undermine the credibility of educational outcomes.

Effective coordination also promotes collaboration among teachers through the organization of assessment panels; peer moderation, and data review sessions, as such, principals can create opportunities for professional learning communities that benefit both professional and non-professional teachers. Hallinger and Murphy (2013) emphasized that collaborative coordination enhances collective efficacy and fosters shared accountability for student learning outcomes. Through this process, non-professional teachers can acquire assessment competencies and improve their instructional delivery.

Finally, the extent of coordination in assessment literacy reflects the leadership effectiveness of school principals. Leaders who prioritize coordination ensure that all instructional processes like planning, teaching, and assessment are systematically integrated. Leithwood et al. (2020) contended that coordinated instructional leadership promotes teacher development, enhances learning quality, and sustains institutional improvement. Therefore, in public senior secondary schools, the degree to which principals coordinate assessment literacy in managing non-professional teachers determines the overall quality of service delivery.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey research design. The aim was to collect information from the respondents' views and opinions to answer the research questions. This design was chosen to assess how non-professional teachers are managed for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

The population of the study comprised all 350 principals in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, including 241 male principals and 109 female principals (Source: Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2024).

The study sampled 350 principals from senior secondary schools in Rivers State, including 241 male principals and 109 female principals (Source: Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2024). A census sampling technique was employed due to the small size of the population.

The research instrument for this study was a 40-item self-constructed questionnaire titled "Managing Non-professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery Questionnaire (MNTESDQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A collected information on the demographic variables of the respondents, while Section B included items designed to gather data for the study. The questionnaire utilized a 4-point modified Likert scale for responses: Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1.

The instrument was validated by three experts in questionnaire development from the Department of Educational Management, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. All suggested corrections were made before finalizing the questionnaire for administration.

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a test-retest method was employed. The instrument was initially administered to 20 principals from Rivers State who were part of the study population but not included in the sample size. After a two-week interval, copies of the same set of instruments were re-administered to the same respondents to assess the consistency of the results. The reliability coefficient was calculated using Cronbach Alpha, and a reliability index of .951 was realized, which indicates a high level of internal consistency and deemed sufficient and acceptable for the study.

A total of 350 copies of the questionnaires were distributed to public senior secondary school principals, with the help of two trained research assistants. The principals were encouraged to complete the questionnaire immediately to ensure a high return rate, though some were allowed

to finish it at their convenience, with follow-up visits made to collect the completed copies. Out of the 350 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 345 copies were returned and used for data analysis, which represented a return rate of 98.57%.

The study used mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, and an independent sample t-test to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level using SPSS version 28. The decisional rule for interpretation of the mean scores was classified using real limits of numbers. Any value from 3.50-4.00 was regarded as Very High Extent, any value from 2.50-3.49 as High Extent, any value from 1.50-2.49 as Low Extent, and any value from 0.50-1.49 as Very Low Extent. For hypotheses testing, the null hypotheses was accepted if the Sig. (2-tailed) value was greater than 0.05 and rejected if it was less than 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent is planning instructional leadership used to manage nonprofessional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent planning instructional leadership was used to manage Non-professional teachers' effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

s/n	Item Statements	Male Principals' N=238		Female Principals' N=107		Mean Set		Decision
		Mean	SD.	Mean	SD.	Mean	SD.	
1	Lesson planning templates help non-professional teachers organize their instructional strategies and activities, making it easier to deliver lessons effectively.	3.28	.53	3.22	.47	3.25	.50	HE
2	Providing opportunities for professional development is essential for improving non-professional teachers' teaching skills.	3.30	.45	3.38	.41	3.24	.43	HE
3	Regular classroom observations of non-professional teachers improve teaching practice.	3.32	.48	3.29	.50	3.31	.49	HE
4	Aligning instructional planning with the curriculum is crucial for non-professional teachers to deliver effective lessons.	3.23	.52	3.28	.48	3.25	.50	HE
5	Establishing clear instructional objectives enhances non-professional teachers' understanding of educational goals.	3.33	.47	3.23	.55	3.28	.51	HE
Grand Mean & SD.		3.29	.49	3.28	.48	3.27	.49	HE

Table 1 presents the mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent is planning instructional leadership used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis presented in the table showed the following range perceptions for items 1 to 5: Lesson planning templates help nonprofessional teachers organize their instructional strategies and activities, making it easier to

deliver lessons effectively (Mean=3.25 and SD=.50), Providing opportunities for professional development is essential for improving non-professional teachers' teaching skills (Mean=3.24 and SD=.43), Regular classroom observations of non-professional teachers improve teaching practice (Mean=3.31 and SD=.49), Aligning instructional planning with the curriculum is crucial for non-professional teachers to deliver effective lessons (Mean=3.25 and SD=.50), and Establishing clear instructional objectives enhances nonprofessional teachers' understanding of educational goals (Mean=3.28 and SD=.51). These indicated that the respondents' perceptions for items 1-5 showed a High Extent, as their mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50–3.49. Furthermore, the table showed a grand mean and standard deviation (Mean = 3.27 and SD = .49), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, and the mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50–3.49. This further implied that, to a high extent, the planning instructional leadership was used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: To what extent is coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state

s/n	Item Statements	Male Principals' N=238		Female Principals' N=107		Mean Set		Decision
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
6	Training in assessment literacy enables non-professional teachers to create fair assessments.	3.15	.69	3.27	.55	3.21	.62	HE
7	Knowledge of assessment literacy improves the feedback provided to students.	3.28	.57	3.20	.61	3.24	.59	HE
8	Non-professional teachers who are literate in assessment are better equipped to meet curriculum standards.	3.26	.55	3.21	.57	3.23	.56	HE
9	Understanding diverse assessment methods is crucial for effective teaching practices.	3.22	.62	3.33	.47	3.28	.55	HE
10	Continuous professional development in assessment literacy is necessary for non-professional teachers.	3.38	.51	3.26	.62	3.32	.57	HE
Grand Mean & SD		3.26	.59	3.25	.56	3.26	.58	HE

Table 2 presents the mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent is coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state. The analysis presented in the above table showed the following range perceptions for items 6 to 10: Training in assessment literacy enables non-professional teachers to create fair assessments (Mean=3.21 and SD=.62), Knowledge of assessment literacy improves the feedback provided to students (Mean=3.24 and SD=.59), Non-professional teachers who are literate in assessment are better equipped to meet curriculum standards (Mean=3.23 and SD=.56), Understanding diverse assessment methods is crucial for

effective teaching practices (Mean=3.28 and SD=.55), and Continuous professional development in assessment literacy is necessary for non-professional teachers (Mean=3.32 and SD=.57). These indicated that the respondents' perceptions for items 6-10 showed a High Extent, as their mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50–3.49. Furthermore, the table showed a grand mean and standard deviation (Mean = 3.26 and SD = .58), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, and the mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50–3.49. This further implies that, to a High Extent, the coordinating assessment literacy was used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning instructional leadership used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning instructional leadership used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents' Category	N(345)	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Male Principals'	238	3.29	.49	343	.323	.567	Accepted
Female Principals'	107	3.28	.48				

Table 3 presents the summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning instructional leadership used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The result from the table shows a calculated t-value of .323, with a significance level (p-value) of .567 at a degree of freedom of 343. Since the p-value is greater than .05, the result is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning instructional leadership was used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents' Category	N(345)	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Male Principals'	238	3.26	.59	343	-.578	.713	Accepted
Female Principals'	107	3.25	.56				

Table 4 presents the summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the

mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent coordinating assessment literacy used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The result from the table shows a calculated t-value of $-.578$, with a significance level (p-value) of $.713$ at a degree of freedom of 343. Since the p-value is greater than $.05$, the result is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent coordinating assessment literacy was used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Planning Instructional Leadership and the Management of Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

The findings in table 1 and 3 revealed to a high extent that planning instructional leadership is used and beneficial to the management of non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, and there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning instructional leadership was used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

These findings are in line with the study of Adebayo and Oyeniran (2022) who found that instructional planning is a crucial function of school leadership that provides the foundation for effective teaching and learning. It involves setting educational goals, developing strategies, allocating resources, and creating structures that guide teachers toward achieving institutional objectives. Non-professional teachers often lack formal pedagogical training, which requires school leaders to adopt deliberate planning approaches to integrate them effectively into the instructional process.

In the same vein, Bush (2011) found that instructional planning provides a systematic approach for achieving educational outcomes by ensuring that instructional activities are organized and coherent. Okon (2019) highlighted that through structured lesson schedules, professional development plans, and instructional supervision timetables, principals can enhance the instructional performance of non-professional teachers and ensure consistency in curriculum delivery.

In the same way, Adeyemi (2020) found that instructional planning provides a framework for identifying skill gaps and implementing remedial interventions, thereby improving teacher performance and student learning outcomes. According to Hallinger and Murphy (2013), goal-oriented planning in schools enhances teachers' sense of purpose and direction. For non-professional teachers, structured planning ensures clarity in lesson delivery and assessment procedures, reducing ambiguity and promoting effective service delivery.

Coordinating Assessment Literacy in the Management of Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

The findings in Table 2 and 4 revealed that respondents to a high extent accept that the coordinating assessment literacy is used and beneficial in the management of non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state, and there was no

significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent coordinating assessment literacy was used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

These findings are in line with the study of (Hallinger (2018) who found that assessment literacy is the ability of teachers to design, administer, interpret, and use assessment data to improve teaching and learning, and the coordination of assessment literacy by instructional leaders ensures that assessment practices are standardized, meaningful, and aligned with curriculum goals.

In the same stratum, Bush (2011) found that when principals coordinate assessment literacy, they organize workshops, develop assessment templates, and ensure that grading systems align with state and national standards. According to Robinson et al. (2008), strong coordination of assessment literacy enhances the coherence of teaching practices and ensures that student assessments reflect actual learning outcomes. For the non-professional teachers, coordination provides the structure and support necessary to implement assessment effectively.

Equally, Leithwood and Jantzi (2006) found that principals play a critical role in guiding teachers to use assessment results for instructional improvement. Through coordinated assessment systems, principals help non-professional teachers understand how to use test data to identify students' learning needs, adjust teaching strategies, and improve lesson effectiveness. Adeyemi (2020) noted that regular coordination meetings, peer assessments, and moderation sessions enable non-professional teachers to improve their judgment of student performance and align their assessments with curriculum objectives.

Hallinger and Murphy (2013) emphasize that collaborative coordination enhances collective efficacy and fosters shared accountability for student learning outcomes. Through this process, non-professional teachers can acquire assessment competencies and improve their instructional delivery.

Finally, the extent of coordination in assessment literacy reflects the leadership effectiveness of school principals. Leaders who prioritize coordination ensure that all instructional processes like planning, teaching, and assessment are systematically integrated. Leithwood et al. (2020) found that coordinated instructional leadership promotes teacher development, enhances learning quality, and sustains institutional improvement.

CONCLUSION

This study on has successfully examined the Planning and Coordinating Roles of Instructional Leadership in Managing Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. The highlighted the critical influence of instructional leadership on teacher performance and school effectiveness. Findings indicate that planning by school principals provides a structured framework for allocating resources, organizing instructional activities, and setting clear teaching and learning goals. Such planning ensures that non-professional teachers, who often lack formal pedagogical training, receive adequate guidance, mentorship, and professional development opportunities, enabling them to contribute effectively to curriculum delivery.

Similarly, coordination, particularly in the area of assessment literacy, plays a significant role in harmonizing teaching and evaluation processes. Principals who actively coordinate instructional activities ensure consistency in lesson delivery, promote collaboration among teachers, and facilitate the use of assessment data to inform teaching strategies. This coordinated approach strengthens accountability, enhances instructional quality, and fosters a positive school climate conducive to learning.

The study establishes that the effective planning and coordinating roles of instructional leadership are indispensable for managing non-professional teachers and improving service delivery in public senior secondary schools. Thus, school leaders can optimize teacher performance, enhance student outcomes, and ensure sustainable educational excellence in Rivers State by combining strategic planning with systematic coordination.

Recommendations

Based on the findings regarding the extent to which instructional planning is used to manage non-professional teachers, it is recommended that:

- Principals of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State should strengthen strategic planning practices. This can include the development of clear instructional goals, structured lesson schedules, and targeted professional development programmes tailored for non-professional teachers.
- School leaders should implement systematic coordination of assessment practices across all teaching staff that can involve regular workshops on assessment design, moderation sessions to standardize grading, and the use of assessment data to inform instructional decisions.

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